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On the granularity gap between perfect and limited forecast control of sustainable energy and hydrogen systems: a case study

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Abstract

Global optimization models, like *Oemof Solph*, tend to under-estimate the net energy costs of disruptive hydrogen technologies by neglecting deep technical insight and decisions under ‘limited forecast’. To address this limitation, our research group is developing a techno-economic tool that realistically evaluates hydrogen system investments by identifying the so called ‘economic granularity gap’ - the difference in cost between idealized and realistic forecasting methods. While global optimization under a ‘perfect forecast’ assumes full knowledge of all future variables, it leads to underestimating the cost and a sub-optimal component sizing. In contrast, ‘limited forecast’ methods, such as agent-based models (ABMs), simulate decision-making with realistic forecast horizons, offering more accurate results, which are coupled, however, with more computational effort. This study aims at estimating the granularity gap between both approaches using a real case study for the County Council building in Landshut, Germany. First, system architectures are assessed economically under ‘perfect forecast’ conditions. Subsequently, the individual components are simulated through technically validated fine models against real experimental data. Finally, the system is simulated under ‘limited forecast’ to evaluate its real-world economic performance and technical feasibility.

It can be concluded that, depending on the investment cost of each specific component, a hybrid energy supply system based on hydrogen components can already be economically competitive compared to a pure electricity grid-based scenario, whereas a system consisting of a photovoltaic system and battery storage, without hydrogen, does represent the optimum solution from a pure economic perspective. In addition, the ‘economic granularity gap’ depends on the installed storage capacity and amounts to 6.59 and 3.32% for the net energy cost and annuity, respectively. Moreover, it turned out that transition cost towards an economical application of a battery storage for the investigated case study amounts to 166€/kWh versus 406 €/kWh for the limited and perfect forecast scenarios, respectively.

Introduction

Despite the ongoing intensification of global warming and the already noticeable impact of climate change, global emissions continue to rise [1]. Among major economies, only the European Union, Japan and USA show a decrease in their annual per capita emissions [2]. Germany, as the main emitter in Europe, shows a good trend in the energy sector, but is, for example, far behind the reduction targets for 2030 in the building sector [3]. Consequently, research and development work must be carried out regarding the use of new sustainable technologies to increase the pace in reducing emissions in sluggish sectors such as buildings. Due to the strong expansion in PV- and wind turbine installations, the electrification of the energy supply for buildings will be a highly effective strategy. Due to volatile generation of electricity and the associated fluctuating electricity prices, energy storage systems might be an alternative way of managing these fluctuations over time to improve the integration of renewable energies in economically feasible solutions. In this context, green hydrogen storage of surplus renewable electricity deems quite suitable for medium- and long-term applications.

1. Scientific Approach

There are various methodological approaches for modelling and optimizing energy systems, whereby the main differentiating feature is the underlying forecasting horizon. Here, a distinction is made between ‘perfect forecast’ and ‘limited forecast’ [4]. Modelling under ‘perfect forecast’ implies that all data such as consumption, generation and electricity price curves for the entire assessment period, for instance a year, are already entirely known at the start of the optimization and become a constitutive part of it. This makes it possible to implement global optimization algorithms that identify the theoretical best case. However, this approach underestimates cost and the storage components are dimensioned sub-optimally compared to the real operating environment [5]. ‘Limited forecast’ approaches include the so-called agent-based models (ABMs). These aim to reflect and optimize the actions of a real marketer in the electricity market with a limited and realistic forecasting horizon. They, therefore, provide more realistic analyses but are more challenging to optimize. The difference in terms of cost between the simulation under ‘perfect forecast’ conditions and the ABMs is termed as the ‘economic granularity gap’ [6].

This study demonstrates how these two methodological approaches can be applied together to provide reliable analyses for sustainable energy and hydrogen systems based on a real case study of the Landshut County Council in Germany. To this aim, a preliminary assessment of the economic potential is carried out for different system architectures tailored to the specific demand by globally optimizing the total cost of ownership (TCO) under ‘perfect forecast’ conditions until end of life. Subsequently, the individual components are simulated through technically validated fine models against real experimental data. This approach enables the consideration of dynamic electrochemical and thermochemical characteristics and losses. In the third step, the system is simulated and optimized based on a practice-oriented control strategy under ‘limited forecast’ conditions, considering the technically fine-modelled components, before it is finally evaluated in terms of economic viability and performance.

2. Simulations

In this work, a case study is carried out for the new construction of the Landshut County Council Building in Landshut, Germany. The consumption data and the generation profiles of the planned rooftop photovoltaic system were provided by the planning company PEMA GmbH und Co KG. The building has an overall electrical annual demand of 992,4 MWh/a

including the electricity demand for the provision of heating and hot water via a heat pump. The already installed photovoltaic system has a peak power of 588,53 kW_p with an annual generation of almost 584,0 MWh/a.

System Architecture – Preliminary Assessment of the economic potential

The technically and economically reasonable utilization of green hydrogen as a seasonal electricity storage system is to be investigated for the building and compared with other energy systems such as a pure photovoltaic with and without a battery storage. Figure 1 shows the developed generic hybrid energy supply concept consisting of the already planned photovoltaic system, a battery-electric storage system and the hydrogen storage system consisting of an electrolyzer, a pressurized hydrogen storage tank and a fuel cell.

Figure 1: Schematic and energy flow diagram of the generic hybrid energy supply system

Furthermore, Figure 1 also shows the planned components for heating, air-conditioning and hot water. This involves the utilization of the waste heat from the hydrogen components for partially covering the heating demand. Within this study, the dimensioning of the hydrogen and heating system was pre-set. As part of the preliminary analysis under ‘perfect forecast’ conditions, all other system components are combined differently and compared with each other within 5 configurations. Table 1 shows the five configurations setup for comparison, with configuration C4 showing the complete hybrid storage concept depicted in Figure 1. As a reference scenario, a “base case” without any application of renewable energy or storage has been chosen.

Table 1: System configurations for the preliminary assessment

Configuration	Abb.	Photovoltaics	Battery	Hydrogen System
Reference	Ref	-	-	-
Configuration 1	C1	✓	-	-
Configuration 2	C2	✓	✓	-
Configuration 3	C3	✓	-	✓
Configuration 4	C4	✓	✓	✓

The size and characteristics of each component are kept identical in every configuration, enabling the direct comparability and making the impact of individual components to be directly visible. An overview on the size and specifications of each component is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Dimensions and specifications of the various components

Component	Parameter	Value	Unit	Ref.
Photovoltaic	Peak power	588,53	kW _p	PEMA
	Generation profile	csv.-data	kW	PEMA
Battery	Nominal capacity	200	kWh _{el}	
	Start/End-SOC	50	%	
	Max. charge and discharging power	0.25C	kW/kWh	
	Min. SOC	10	%	
	Max. SOC	80	%	
	Charge and discharge efficiency	98	%	
Electrolyzer	Nominal power	150	kW _{el}	
	Efficiency (Higher Heating Value)	75,52	%	[7]
Fuel Cell	Nominal power	50	kW _{el}	
	Efficiency (Higher Heating Value)	47,20	%	[8]
Hydrogen storage	Max. storage capacity	20.000	kWh _{HHV}	
	Min. pressure	35	bar	
	Min. SOC	6.5	%	
	Max. pressure	350	bar	
	Max. SOC	100	%	

The storage units are dimensioned in such a way that, the battery is able to secure the energy supply for at least three hours during the working periods just in case of a blackout. Additionally, due to its size, the hydrogen storage system is able to fully cover a typical week's consumption, for example during a prolonged period of low solar power generation. The preliminary assessment of the individual system architectures is based on the total cost of ownership (TCO) in €/a. This describes the expected annual cost for the system operator, which according to equation (1) are made up of the annual depreciations and the net energy cost. As the energy supply system in this case is purely electricity-based, the net energy cost result from the electricity cost deducted by the potential revenues by feed-in tariffs from the electrical grid.

$$TCO = Annuity + Net Energy Costs \quad (1)$$

The annuity in equation (1) is estimated by equation (2) for the sum of the annuities of all individual components j with the configuration-dependent quantity k of components.

$$Annuity = \sum_{j=1}^k CRF_j * Invest_j + Maint_j = \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{i * (1 + i)^{n_j}}{(1 + i)^{n_j} - 1} * Invest_j + Maint_j \quad (2)$$

The Capital Replacement Factor (CRF) is calculated using an interest rate of $i = 0.04$ and the respective expected lifetime of the components. Consequently, the annuity remains constant over the entire project period and makes it possible to estimate the actual arising

costs. The initial investment and the annual maintenance costs for the individual components result from the specific CAPEX and OPEX in relation to the respective dimensioning of each component. All annuities for the individual components are listed in Table 3, where the sum of all components represents the total annuity for configuration C4.

Table 3: Calculation of the individual annuities

Component	Dim.	CAPEX	OPEX	LT	Annuity	Ref.
Photovoltaic	588,53 [kW _p]	900 [€/kW _p]	13 [€/kW _p /a]	30 [a]	38.282,16 [€/a]	[9,10]
Battery	200 [kWh _{el}]	300 [€/kWh]	5 [€/kWh _{el} /a]	15 [a]	6.396,47 [€/a]	[9]
Electrolyzer	150 [kW _{el}]	1.100 [€/kW _{el}]	20 [€/kW _{el} /a]	15 [a]	17.840,28 [€/a]	[11]
Fuel Cell	50 [kW _{el}]	1.834 [€/kW _{el}]	1%*CAPEX [€/a]	15 [a]	9.164,60 [€/a]	[12]
H ₂ -Storage	20.000 [kWh _{H₂}]	11,42 [€/kWh _{H₂}]	1%*CAPEX [€/a]	20 [a]	19.090,07 [€/a]	[13]
Heat Pump	326,50 [kW _{th}]	500 [€/kW _{th}]	0,5%*CAPEX [€/a]	15 [a]	15.499,13 [€/a]	[9]
Heat Storage	1000 [kWh _{th}]	30 [€/kWh _{th}]	0,45 [€/kWh _{th} /a]	25 [a]	2.370,36 [€/a]	[9]
Electric Boiler	35 [kW _{th}]	306,67 [€/kW _{th}]	1%*CAPEX [€/a]	15 [a]	1.072,71 [€/a]	[9]
Total					109.715,79 [€/a]	

The net energy cost are optimized during the preliminary evaluation with the help of *Oemof Solph* [14], which is a linear optimization open-source tool that uses the ‘perfect forecast’ method to determine a global minimum of net energy cost for a given system architecture by means of an optimal control. In this tool, all components and especially the hydrogen components are modelled in a very simplified manner. For example, the hydrogen production or consumption rate is calculated using the constant efficiencies defined in Table 2. Modulation ranges, start-up times and dynamic ramp-up and shut-down effects, for example, are not considered, which means that, the components are always available at their nominal operation conditions. Such a modelling approach is referred to as “coarse modelling” throughout the remaining course of this work.

Technical fine modeling and component dimensioning

With the technical fine modelling, it is meant to apply more detailed models for the same system architecture as in the preliminary analysis, with each being validated against experimental data. In addition, necessary peripheral components, such as the hydrogen compressor between the electrolyzer and the pressurized storage tank, are also considered. Strictly speaking, an electrochemical and thermal model according to Espinosa-Lopez [15] is used for the electrolyzer. This enables the precise calculation of the hydrogen production rate via the temperature-dependent cell voltages and the dynamic simulation of the average stack temperature. Additionally, the modulation range, start-up times and ramp-up effects are considered. The specific input parameters for the electrochemical model were calculated using an in-house developed particle-swarm algorithm based on experimental data from a 100kW PEM electrolysis stack [16], which is scaled up to the 150kW stack level by enhancing the number of cells. The input parameters for the thermal model are determined by the experimentally confirmed interpolation approach according to [16]. Similar models have been used for the fuel cell [17]. However, no experimental data was available for a power class of 50 kW. Therefore, an efficiency extrapolation over the modulation range of a real 80 kW PEM fuel cell is used to calculate the hydrogen consumption [18], taking the nominal power of the applied FC into consideration. Real market models with their associated efficiency curves over the modulation range are also used to simulate the battery. These are based on the database of the commercially available software *PVSOL* [19]. An overview of the input parameters and market models used is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Input parameters for the technical fine models

Component	Parameter	Value	Unit	Ref
Electrolyzer	Anode charge transfer coefficient α	0.5131	-	[16]
	Standard anode exchange current density $i_{0,an,std}$	6,70e-8	A/cm ²	[16]
	Activation energy for anode electron transport E_{Exc}	35986	J/mol	[16]
	Electrical conductivity MEA at std. conditions $\sigma_{mem,std}$	0.0638	S/cm	[16]
	Activation energy for proton transport in MEA E_{Pro}	11557	J/mol	[16]
	Lumped thermal capacity of the stack C_{th}	171827	J/K	[16]
	Lumped thermal resistance of the stack R_{th}	0,129	K/W	[16]
	Losses due to the peripherals (e.g. gas rectifier)	5	%	
Fuel Cell	Load-dependent efficiency of the stack	csv.-data	%	[18]
	Additional losses due to the peripherals	5	%	
Battery	Market model: Growatt New Energy Co./WIT 100K-HU	-	-	[19]
	Load-dependent efficiency	csv.-data	%	[19]

The technically detailed modelling approach enables a precise calculation of the waste heat output with corresponding temperature levels, enabling the development of realistic control units and operating concepts explicitly for the heat components within a specific system configuration. In this work, such a model was created for the hydrogen-based hybrid energy supply system (C4) and compared with the previous preliminary analysis.

Financial Assessment under ‘limited forecast’ conditions

The final evaluation of a specific system architecture is carried out with the technical detailed model and a control unit using a so-called agent-based model approach, which is intended to reflect the behavior of a direct marketer as accurately as possible under ‘limited forecast’ conditions. In our model, algorithmic decisions are made under “ad-hoc” prices following the merit order principle for the available storage options (power grid, battery or hydrogen) considering variable states of charge and electricity tariffs. For each storage option the specific storage cost (ct/kWh) was determined, and all available options were prioritized accordingly against the fallback option of feeding the electricity surplus back into the grid. It is noteworthy that *Oemof Solph*, does not take depreciation into account as part of its global optimization. In order to compare under the same baseline, component degradation of battery, hydrogen etc. were subsequently not taken into account as part of the technical fine-model and it was assumed that the expected lifetime is achieved in any case. Technical fine-modelling was mainly deployed to address latency times and dynamic ramp-up and shut-down effects, which do not allow an immediate dispatch of the full capacity of the respective device when needed. In reality, it is well known that expected lifetime especially for hydrogen components is significantly influenced by the operational control strategy [20], a fact that will be addressed in another communication.

3. Results

In the preliminary assessment, the various system architectures are compared with the reference case, i.e. without any renewable energy components, and among each other. This was carried out for the Landshut County Council case study exemplary for the year 2024, and the results of this comparison are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Annuities of the different system architectures for the Landshut County Council case study under different electricity price scenarios

First, the comparison of the reference configuration reveals that the annuity is significantly more favorable under the dynamic electricity price in 2024 than under the static price scenario. This is because the average dynamic electricity price of 23,47 ct/kWh in 2024 was significantly cheaper than the fixed, or static, price of 40,11 ct/kWh. However, supply via a purely dynamic tariff also entails a higher risk of bearing the full weight of sharp price increases, such as after the start of the Russian-Ukraine war in 2022, meaning that most electricity market participants secure part of their energy consumption via long-term contracts at static prices. If energy consumption is covered partly by static and partly by dynamic contracts, this is referred to as a hybrid procurement strategy [21]. Depending on the share and price of the static part, the net energy costs and thus the annuities in Figure 2 would lie between these two values.

When comparing the different configurations with the reference case, it is noticeable that each configuration can reduce and improve the expected annuity costs. Strictly speaking, the savings in net energy costs are higher than the additional depreciation of the components applied. It is noticeable that, the photovoltaic system alone already achieves considerable savings of 28,56 % and 19,00 % under static and dynamic pricing conditions, respectively. This is referred to the fact that, the generation profile and consumption profile match very well due to the working hours of the employees around lunch time and, therefore, a high self-consumption share of the generated PV power of 66,39% can already be achieved in this configuration. This means that, there is a low potential for shifting PV electricity for the hydrogen components. The net energy cost in cases C3 and C4 can be further reduced significantly by the storage system, but the high amortization costs of the additional components lead to a higher annuity than in C1. The most favorable configuration is configuration C2 with the photovoltaic system and the battery storage. The global minimum annuity is achieved for the static electricity pricing scenario at a battery capacity of 291 kWh instead of the assumed value of 200kWh in Table 3 and for the dynamic scenario at a battery capacity of 205 kWh.

The preliminary analysis revealed that, although the hydrogen-based hybrid storage system (C4) is not the most economical alternative, it is still advantageous if compared with the reference configuration, even with a fully dynamic electricity price in 2024. For this reason, this configuration is subjected to a more detailed sensitivity analysis in the remaining part of this paper. Figure 2 depicts the obtained results for the ‘economic granularity gap’ once with the coarse technical model and once with the technical fine model at various battery storage capacities for the hybrid energy storage configuration (C4).

a) Absolute annuity

b) Relative increase in annuity compared to 'perfect forecast'

c) Absolute net energy costs

b) Relative increase in net energy cost compared to 'perfect forecast'

Figure 3: Investigation results of the 'economic granularity gap' by the application of 'limited forecast' vs. 'perfect forecast' and technically detailed fine models

The annuity in Figure 3a under 'perfect forecast' at 200 kWh battery capacity corresponds to the previous result from the preliminary analysis. If the battery capacity is varied, the trend in Figure 3a identifies a minimum, or an optimum storage capacity of 113 kWh under 'perfect forecast' conditions. In comparison, in the simulation with the priority list (limited forecast), the annuity cost exclusively increases when the battery capacity is increased as shown by the orange curve in Figure 3a. The rise in cost results from the fact that less energy cost savings can be achieved without any prediction. This is illustrated in Figure 3c, as the 'perfect forecast' method can achieve significantly more savings with increasing battery capacity. To be specific, the net energy cost in the example of 200 kWh battery capacity, as shown in Figure 3d, are 5.28% higher solely due to the optimization methodology.

Additionally, the cost does increase further, if the detailed and experimentally validated technical fine model is applied together with the control via the priority list for the hybrid storage system. This is almost exclusively due to the lower average efficiency of the hydrogen components, which is why the relative rise remains almost constant over the entire observation range, mainly due to the detailed technical modelling in Figures 3b and 3d. It is also important to mention that, the cost increment due to the detailed technical modelling can be significantly higher in a simulation with a higher temporal resolution of the load curve

and the generation profile [17]. Finally, as a core conclusion, the comparison implies not only increased costs, but above all, that a stationary battery under ‘limited forecast’ conditions does not provide any financial added value, as the lowest annuity is achieved without this component.

However, this conclusion is largely dependent on the expected investment costs of the battery. Figure 4 illustrates, therefore, the results of a sensitivity analysis of how this parameter affects the dimensioning of the battery. This analysis is carried out once under ‘perfect forecast’ and once with the detailed technical model under ‘limited forecast’ by the priority list.

Figure 4: Sensitivity analysis of the battery’s CAPEX on the optimum nominal capacity

Figure 4 shows the previously presented minimum under ‘perfect forecast’ at a CAPEX value of 300 €/kWh with an optimum battery storage capacity of 113 kWh. If more favorable investment costs could be achieved on the market, then this optimal capacity increases according to the trend line in Figure 4. Furthermore, the marginal cost can be determined at the intersection of the trend line with the abscissa, indicating the marginal costs above which the battery would no longer be applied for economic reasons, even under ‘perfect forecast’ conditions. This limit amounts to €406/kWh. The sensitivity analysis also provides similar findings for the detailed technical model under ‘limited forecast’. In this case, however, the investment cost must be significantly lower and at least below €166/kWh for the application of battery storage within the hydrogen-based energy supply system (C4) to be economically beneficial.

In addition to the battery, a sensitivity analysis of the investment costs of the hydrogen components is particularly important, as the electrolysis and fuel cell units do entail the highest CAPEX. In the literature, these can vary between 500 to 2500 €/kW_{el} for the electrolyzer [11] and between 500 to 3500 €/kW_{el} for the fuel cell [12]. The results of this analysis for the detailed technical model under ‘limited forecast’ conditions are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Sensitivity analysis of the hydrogen component's CAPEX on the annuity

The dashed white line in Figure 5 indicates the annuity costs of the reference configuration without renewable energy components. Depending on the investment costs of the two components, this analysis can be used to directly determine, whether the application of the hybrid energy storage system is profitable compared to the reference case. The analysis demonstrates that the system, in this case study, can only be competitive at the most favorable prices currently available in the market. However, the manufacturing prices for hydrogen components will continue to drop significantly in the coming years, making hybrid energy systems based on green hydrogen more and more interesting. Finally, it is important to note that, this study relates exclusively to the year 2024. For a reliable planning basis, a so-called risk of investment analysis must be carried out, which will be the subject of one of our subsequent publications.

4. Conclusions

The obtained results of the investigated case study demonstrate that, depending on the investment cost of each specific component, a hybrid energy supply system based on hydrogen storage components can already be economically competitive compared to a pure electricity grid-based scenario, whereas a system consisting of a photovoltaic system and battery storage without hydrogen still represents the economically optimum solution. In addition, the 'economic granularity gap' depending on the installed storage capacities is quantitatively estimated for the investigated case study to be 6.59% more net energy cost and 3.32% higher annuity. In addition, a methodology is presented on how certain components, such as a battery in a hybrid hydrogen-based storage system, can be optimally dimensioned depending on their specific investment costs. The results demonstrated that the marginal cost for the application of a battery in this system is 166€/kWh under more realistic (limited forecast) conditions compared to 406€/kWh under the 'perfect forecast' scenario. Finally, the sensitivity analysis of the specific investment costs for the electrolyzer and the fuel cell indicates that the use of hydrogen can certainly be competitive with currently realistic market prices compared to a purely grid-based scenario under a dynamic electricity pricing. In summary, the multi-step approach of the techno-economic design and evaluation tool allows a time-effective optimization of future hybrid energy systems with reliable technical and financial predictions. By using experimentally validated technical models for the hydrogen components and a system control with a 'limited forecast' horizon, a close-to-reality analysis can be conducted.

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